

***Larinus vulpes* (Olivier, 1807), a new weevil species in the fauna of Hungary
(Coleoptera: Curculionidae)**

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Abstract – The first reliable records of *Larinus vulpes* (Olivier, 1807) (Coleoptera: Curculionidae: Lixinae: Lixini) from Central Europe and Hungary are presented. The species has been found in several locations of the Kiskunság National Park and adjacent areas, on the known host plant *Echinops ritro* subsp. *ruthenicus* (M. Bieb.) Nym. (Asteraceae).

Key words – new record, faunistics, distribution, Lixinae

INTRODUCTION

The weevil genus *Larinus* Dejean, 1821 (Coleoptera: Curculionidae) belongs to the tribe Lixini Schoenherr, 1823 of the subfamily Lixinae; the tribe contains approximately 180 valid species, more than 110 of which are known from the Palaearctic Region (TER-MINASSIAN 1967, GÜLTEKIN 2006, ALONSO-ZARAZAGA *et al.* 2023).

Larinus vulpes (Olivier, 1807) is known from southern, south-eastern and eastern Europe, North Africa, the Middle East, and Central Asia (ALONSO-ZARAZAGA *et al.* 2023). The species has not been known from Central Europe, except some historical records from Slovakia (PURKYNĚ 1954); however, these were considered insufficiently documented and questionable (BENEDIKT *et al.* 2022). The species has not been reported from Hungary so far (cf. PODLUSSÁNY *et al.* 2019, ALONSO-ZARAZAGA *et al.* 2023).

Larinus vulpes prefers open, sunny areas such as primary and degraded steppe lands, slopes, limestone and chalk cliffs of low mountains (SKUHROVEC *et al.* 2017). Larvae feed within the flowers of globe thistles (*Echinops* spp., Asteraceae); in Ukraine, immature stages were observed to develop in flowers of

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Echinops ritro subsp. *ruthenicus* (M. Bieb.) Nym. and *Echinops sphaerocephalus* L. (SKUHROVEC *et al.* 2017). Adults feed on leaves and stems; highest level of adult activity has been observed at the end of June (TER-MINASSIAN 1967, SKUHROVEC *et al.* 2017).

Figs 1–5. *Larinus vulpes* (Olivier, 1807), 1 = adult on its host plant from Fülöpháza Sand Dunes, 2 = freshly emerged specimen with tomentum, 3 = habitat, 4 = host plant, 5 = flower deformed by larva or pupa (photos by Filip Trnka (Figs 1, 3–5) and Valentin Szénási (Fig. 2))

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Taxonomy and nomenclature follow ALONSO-ZARAZAGA *et al.* (2023).

Abbreviations for depositories – CBS = private collection of Béla Szelenczey (Győr, Hungary), CFT = private collection of Filip Trnka (Tršice, Czech Republic), CJK = private collection of Jiří Krátký (Hradec Králové, Czech Republic), CVS = private collection of Valentin Szénási (Isaszeg, Hungary), HNHM = Hungarian National Museum Public Collection Centre – Hungarian Natural History Museum (Budapest, Hungary).

RESULTS

Larinus vulpes (Olivier, 1807)
(Figs 1–2)

Material examined – **Hungary: Bács-Kiskun County:** Kiskunság National Park, Fülöpháza, Sand Dunes (Fig. 3), 46°51'54.00"N, 19°24'42.48"E, 29.VI.2024, leg. & det. J. Krátký & F. Trnka (4 specimens in CFT, 4 specimens in CJK, 2 specimens in HNHM); Fülöpháza, Strázsa-hill, 46°52'11.63"N, 19°24'32.33"E, 13.VII.2024, leg. & det. V. Szénási (2 specimens in CVS); Fülöpháza, Strázsa-hill, 46°52'05.55"N, 19°24'39.84"E, 2.VIII.2024, leg. & det. V. Szénási (2 specimens in CVS, 1 specimen in HNHM); Jakabszállás, Baromjárás, 46°44'35.73"N, 19°38'28.60"E, 13.VIII.2024, leg. & det. V. Szénási & B. Szelenczey (2 specimens in CVS, 4 specimens in CBS); Jakabszállás, Öreg-forest, 46°43'58.04"N, 19°38'51.45"E, 13.VIII.2024, leg. & det. V. Szénási & B. Szelenczey (2 specimens in CVS, 2 specimens in CBS); Bócsa, Bócsai-forest, 46°40'22.19"N, 19°29'24.41"E, 21.VIII.2024, leg. & det. V. Szénási (1 specimen in CVS); Kaskantyú, Bócsai-forest, 46°41'17.11"N, 19°27'42.31"E, 21.VIII.2024, leg. & det. V. Szénási (1 specimen in CVS); Orgovány, Bócsai-forest, 46°42'24.50"N, 19°27'52.71"E, 21.VIII.2024, leg. & det. V. Szénási (1 specimen in CVS, 1 specimen in HNHM); Bugac, Bugaci-forest, 46°38'26.76"N, 19°37'42.27"E, 24.VIII.2024, leg. & det. V. Szénási (1 specimen in CVS); Móricgát, Kalmár-field, 46°36'44.61"N, 19°43'01.64"E, 24.VIII.2024, leg. & det. V. Szénási (1 specimen in CVS); Kiskunmajsa, near Kukorica-hill, 46°31'18.10"N, 19°36'57.35"E, 24.VIII.2024, leg. & det. V. Szénási (1 specimen in CVS); between Kunfehértó and Kiskunhalas, 46°23'18.97"N, 19°26'33.51"E, 24.VIII.2024, leg. & det. V. Szénási (1 specimen in CVS); between Zsana and Kiskunmajsa, Tajó, 46°25'31.35"N, 19°40'35.19"E, 31.VIII.2024, leg. & det. V. Szénási (3 specimens in CVS); Kiskunmajsa, Tajó, 46°25'33.68"N, 19°40'17.66"E, 31.VIII.2024, leg. & det. V. Szénási (1 specimen in CVS); Izsák, Matyó, 46°46'08.14"N, 19°18'17.72"E, 3.IX.2024, leg. & det. V. Szénási (2 specimens in CVS). **Pest County:** Táborfalva, Madarasi-hill, 47°03'49.06"N, 19°27'20.92"E, 2.IX.2024, leg. & det. V. Szénási (3 specimens in CVS).

Remarks – First records of the species from Hungary. All specimens were singled or swept from *Echinops ritro* subsp. *ruthenicus* (Fig. 4). Many infested flowers have also been observed (Fig. 5). The last author also made repeated attempts to find the species on *Echinops sphaerocephalus*, but without success, despite that these two congeneric host plants grew together in several localities visited. Proposed Hungarian name: “szamárkenyér-püderbarkó”.

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